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**PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE DESIGNER'S PROFESSIONAL
ACTIVITY
ПСИХОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ПРОФЕСІЙНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ
ДИЗАЙНЕРА**

У тезах дизайн визначено як творчу проєктно-художню діяльність, пов'язану зі генерацією образу предметного світу, спрямовану на формування гармонійного предметного середовища, що задовольняє потреби людини, у результаті якої створюється творчий продукт або інший результат цієї діяльності. Охарактеризовано психологічний зміст художньо-графічної, проєктної, конструкторської, технічної та технологічної складових діяльності дизайнера.

Ключові слова: дизайн, дизайнер, компоненти професійної діяльності дизайнера.

A designer is a specialist in the field of designing the object world, creating products necessary for human life, armed with the sum of various knowledge, able to fully realize their ideas about the social needs of society in a specific material object. Design education, being in the process of formation, is naturally aimed at a humanitarian worldview, the development of a humanistic style of thinking of a new generation of designers in independent Ukraine. Art education for the formation of professional competence of a designer is the basis for the realization of the creative potential of a design student. Design education is aimed at studying project methodology, methods of structural organization of form, based on purpose, socio-cultural function, and the possibilities of technological implementation of design development in production. Today, it is necessary to increase the level of professional training of designers, further study the possibility of design in the field of production, which would allow to coordinate the joint work of the designer with the technologist and other specialists, which makes it possible to achieve the final effect of design (Прохоров, А. М. & Гусаева, 1987).

The English word «design» (from the English design – to design, draw, conceive, as well as project, plan, drawing) has become a term that means a type of activity for designing the subject world (Дизайн: Словник-довідник, 2010, р. 121), and it comes from the Italian «disegno», which means not only a drawing or a picture, but also complex things – almost the entire field of the artist's work, with the exception of easel art (Глазычев, 2006, р. 13). Initially, this word characterized the specific activities of artists in the field of designing and implementing holistic interior design, but today the definition proposed by the prominent designer T. Maldonado and approved at the ICSID (International

Council of Societies of Industrial Design) Congress in London in 1969 is generally accepted: «Design is a creative activity that aims to define the formal properties of industrial products. These properties include the external features of the product, but mainly those structural and functional relationships that transform the product into a single whole from the point of view of both the consumer and the manufacturer» (Черняк, 2006, р. 12-13).

Design as an activity reflects its procedural essence, but the result of such creative artistic and design activity is an image or a finished creative product. Design as a creative process, method, and result of artistic and technical design is focused on achieving maximum compliance of the created objects and the environment with the utilitarian and aesthetic needs of a person. The designer's goal can be to solve design problems from the smallest detail of a household structure to complex mental constructions and global philosophical ideas. Therefore, the object of design is a material or ideal object that is subject to design transformation or modification in order to achieve the desired technical parameters (constructiveness, functionality, comfort, etc.) or aesthetic or social appeal. Thus, design today is a new, highly complex field of professional activity and, at the same time, a multi-level system of interdisciplinary knowledge that claims to be a separate science (Демків, 2021).

The essence of design activity is the prognostic orientation of creativity, the ability to combine a holistic image of the future, the specificity of creative development of reality, creative imagination and special non-standard thinking. The difference between design and other types of design activity lies in the dynamism of processes and the constant changeability of forms (Сидоренко, 1994).

In the psychology of professional activity, discussions about the psychological content of design as an activity are relevant today, since the complexity of this phenomenon, the variety of types and areas of application do not allow it to be unambiguously reduced to artistic and design, artistic and graphic, artistic and technical, artistic and engineering, or creative activities. O.P. Golikova and T.A. Shevchuk believe that design is a specific project activity that combines artistic and subject matter creativity and engineering practice (цит за Демків, 2021). S.M. Mikhailov and L.M. Kuleeva note that today design is a complex interdisciplinary design and artistic activity that integrates natural science, technical, humanitarian knowledge, engineering and artistic thinking, aimed at forming an industrialized subject world in an extremely large «zone of contact» with a person in all spheres of life without exception (Мелик-Пашаев, 1981). A.G. Dmytruk defines design as a creative activity of artistic construction (design) of industrial products in accordance with the laws of beauty and functionality, understanding it as an activity of harmonizing attitudes towards the subject world, its creation in accordance with the measure of a person and the measure of the phenomena of the subject world (Дмитрук, 1985).

Thus, design is a creative design and artistic activity related to the generation of an image of the object world, aimed at forming a harmonious object environment that meets human needs, which results in a creative product or other result of this activity.

The profession of a future designer involves knowledge of the laws of composition, painting, graphics, equipment, technology, sculpture, etc., which also requires the ability to analyze the market and consumers, psychological awareness, the ability to perceive and choose appropriate visual means, and effective solutions to the task set by the customer (Фалько, 2007).

V. F. Sidorenko wrote that the peculiarity of designers is their mastery of ways of «metaphorical understanding» of the world. The designer knows the language of objects, hears what they say, and is endowed with the ability to create new objects that will carry new messages (Сидоренко, 1994).

S.V. Chirchuk has identified several substantive varieties (directions) of the designer's professional activity, which include: 1) artistic and graphic activity of the designer, which consists in mastering at a perfect and high professional level the skills of project graphics, types of artistic and graphic techniques and technical means, artistic design, modeling and modeling, awareness of the elements and laws of composition, manifestation of aesthetic taste; 2) design activity of the designer, based on the methodology and phasing of work on the task, perfect mastery of the professional features of planning the creative process of architectural and artistic design and performance skills, creating design projects; professional work with reference and thematic literature, documents, standards, the ability to systematize thematic material, search sketching and clause, designing individual elements of a complex environmental design project, etc; 3) design activity of the designer, which consists in the skillful use of methodological, regulatory technical and other directive materials, design of individual elements and complexes under the guidance of leading experts, taking into account the requirements of ergonomics and aesthetics of production and life, in accordance with the requirements of a unified system of design and technical documentation ability to search for optimal and rational options for a constructive solution; 4) technical activity of a designer based on his/her professional level skills in project graphics, types of graphic techniques and technical means of layout, techniques and technical means of performance, ability to professionally use modern technical means of computer graphics in his/her creative and performance work, use technical means and professional skills to perform constructive drawings and templates, prepare an explanatory note in accordance with the scope of the project and the requirements of applicable standards, mastery of graphic techniques, technical means of three-dimensional plastic modeling, using the best domestic and foreign experience of industrial design, develop technical and supporting documentation for design projects with professional use of computer equipment or traditional technologies; 5) technological activity of the designer, which is based on awareness of the

technology of materials (construction, finishing, monumental and decorative) for the application of the latest design technologies in creative and performance activities, the ability to draw up a technological map of industrial replication of the designed product based on knowledge of material technology, labor protection, safety requirements, industrial sanitation, ecology, production technology and skillfully use the latest design technologies (Чирчик, 2017). To summarize, the designer's activity should combine the following components: subject creativity, technical aesthetics, artistic design and construction, industrial art, and understanding of general and highly specialized problems of professional activity (Дружинин, 1999). All these types of professional activities of a designer are the content of his or her creative activity and are embodied in his or her professional competence.